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Values of Trust and Social Cohesion in the Modern Socio-Cultural Space

Abstract: *Introduction.* Nowadays is the very actual task for the thinkers, academicians and practitioners how to overcome challenges and threats of COVID-19 pandemic in the pedagogical, educational and social cultural spheres. It demands some researches and practical steps in the socio-cultural space development. The basic principles of effective development of modern socio-cultural space, based on the values of trust and social cohesion, are considered in the article. Modern geopolitical processes at the epicenter of which Ukraine is, its complex and uncertain reality in the socio-cultural sphere, and poses multifactorial problems that require thorough educational and scientific research. *Purpose and methods.* One of the main task is to research in which way the values of trust and, accordingly, social cohesion to be manifested in the social cultural space. The model of social cohesion and methods of its measurement are considered. The article applies the historical method and method of system analysis to outline the main features of European values, in particular, trust and social cohesion in the socio-cultural space of Ukrainian society. *Results.* The model of social cohesion and methods of its measurement are considered. Also various concepts and manifestations of trust as a factor of social cohesion in the contemporary socio-cultural space are considered. *Conclusions.* This research reflects and proves the confident role of education in the development of social cohesion of communities at the different dimensions of socio-cultural space. The article investigated the effective socio-cultural communications that shape the social cultural space is based on the values of trust and social cohesion. Certain challenges of today require not only research, but also practical methods of implementation,

development of trust and social cohesion in communities at the different levels of socio-cultural space.

Keywords: education, educational community, trust, social cohesion, socio-cultural space, values.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Nowadays we are experiencing the changes of social and cognitive paradigm, in particular, in its socio-cultural focus. Modern crisis tendencies are sufficiently increased and multiplied by the pandemic situation. They are interfered with the world financial and economic crisis. This complex situation actualizes the present and shaped the appearing problems of the modern socio-cultural dimension. The socio-cultural dimension is the “bottleneck” of the changes in the Ukrainian and worldwide communities. At first, we can notice the problem of the virtualization of social cultural dimension. Also, there are many very unpleasant changes in the everyday life of the quite a big amount of society members. Many spheres of the social cultural activity are getting worth: in particular, industry of hospitality, creative industries, media etc. are changing very fast. It should be noticed that these changes are unpredictable, non-linear and turbulent. And the above changes are expanding to the other socio-cultural spheres. Definitely, we are experiencing the appearance of the totally different cognitive and social niche of humans. For instance, not only the “pioneers” of the virtual digital world, the so-called “down-shifters” who have chosen work format outside the office, but also ordinary representatives of traditional forms of doing business are now forced to change their cognitive practices, lifestyles, “means of production” and socio-cultural communications. There are signs/challenges of the present unpredictable social reality. To be not adaptive but proactive to its challenges the main task of the modern system of education (in particular, in social cultural sphere) is to offer the new standards of teaching & learning technologies. They have to cover many important issues in the terms of pandemic – virtualization & digitalization and physical and social distance, loss of habitual dimension etc. One of the most actual and complicate challenge is disconnection, which leads to the divided branched society, couples, and business and production teams: actual modern challenges of social life will impact on the all stages of the social organization.

State study of the problem. So, these changes actualize researches of the complex social phenomenon, philosophical concept of social cohesion. While this concept is rather new, as its basic principles were formulated within the framework of the Council of Europe only in 1990, already there are many

studies associated with it: EU Social Cohesion Policy, Social Cohesion Radar, Social Cohesion Model etc. (Dragolov et al., 2013). The study of social cohesion is actual for the analyze of the social cultural space because it highlights the “weak points” of social relations and other very important problem of social cultural areas (Bondarenko et al., 2017). It can be noted that not only Ukraine, but also the European Union and other countries of the world are currently undergoing a process of rapid political and demographic change, which actualizes the search for a sustainable platform of values for successful coexistence and social development.

We can state that the EU values and norms seem to be the most important tool of social organization of European Union and other European countries. According to the main social idea of EU – to create the society of shared common values which will launch the appropriate social-economic development processes.

This task was quite difficult before the pandemic. Many researchers and observers noticed the crucial loss of European values, migration crisis and an infringement of human rights and fundamental freedoms. New social situation of pandemic confirmed that the actual challenge for all countries (not only for the European Union or Ukraine) is the revision of their real (not decalred) set of values. According to this revised set of values the priorities in social and educational policies should be stated (Nesterova, 2020). The values are manifesting in the social cultural space, at first, in the educational space – the modern education definitely should be based on the values (Blum, 2014). The values determine the level of social cohesion in the society and its features as a social phenomenon. The social cohesion is based on the set of individual and collective values. Because of this value-based platform it could integrate modern divided societies, various levels communities. The values are drivers of human behaviour and they should occupy the significant space of all social innovations i.e. education, in particular (Social Cohesion and Education).

Social cohesion, according to European experience, is one of the factors and guarantors of social stability, tolerant relations between government and citizens in a global economic and political instability. It supports all large-scale organizational, structural and financial and economic changes. For several decades, the development of social cohesion has been one of the most important tasks announced in the documents, protocols and other working materials of the European Union. The EU Social Cohesion Policy reflects the importance of this phenomenon for the European socio-cultural space development. Also, we can consider the social cohesion in a value focus as it is the one of the most important working value of the European Union – support of the complex conglomerate of the European countries with the different levels of prosperity, inclusion et al.

In fact, the European Union itself is essentially a union of values: the European integration project is a project of common values, which is stated in various strategic documents of the European Commission (Shcherbakova, 2014). Thus, European values were partly enshrined in the Declaration of European Identity, adopted in 1973 in Copenhagen by the European Society (the name of the European Union when it consisted of nine member states). “Europe's identity, according to this document, was based on a common heritage, based on the following values: an identical attitude to life, based on the idea of creating a society in accordance with the needs of the people; principles of effective democracy; equality before the law; social justice and respect for human rights” (Shcherbakova, 2014, p. 6). Unfortunately, these, primarily political, values have not become fully the real values of the United Europe, as we see after the first crisis trials that the European (and, in general, world) community is currently struggling with. It is possible that right now research in the field of values, their development will become even more relevant for all countries of the common European space, as well as those who seek to join it. Some theoretical research has already been carried out, such as the classification of the values of a united Europe, the criteria of which have been developed on the basis of data of “Europe an Values Survey”, “European Social Survey”, “Eurobarometer”, as well as content analysis data contained in the “Treaty establishing a Constitution for Europe”. Also a key document is the Lisbon Treaty; in addition, it is advisable to take into account the method of qualitative analysis of documents – the Copenhagen criteria (Shcherbakova, 2014). Values act as a certain guiding parameter (according to the synergetic methodology) for complex social systems. Such as, for example, the European Union.

Unresolved issues. But values, in turn, are also a complex social concept. Thus, we can note the duality of the concept of values: “Value is a strong belief that a certain type of behavior is more important in the existing cultural continuum. Values exist in the social consciousness and are internalized by the individual” (Suprun, 1987, p. 162). This duality is clearly demonstrated by the example of the value of social cohesion, which is perceived by the individual and realized at the level of society. It can also be noted for the value of trust, which is also personalized, but “felt” at the highest levels of social organization. Trust as a phenomenon is “intrapersonal”, which is manifested in the interpersonal space, “carried” into the space of interpersonal relations. Trust is the basis of socio-cultural communication, it to some extent performs the function of communication between people. And trust makes this connection subjective and deeply dialogical. The value dimension of trust is also in the fact that communication is not only and not so much informational, but is inter-

personal, by mutual consent, influence. And this mutual influence of the subjects of socio-cultural communication occurs under the condition that they treat themselves and others as an autonomous sovereign subject of activity and as a value (Nazaruk, 2010).

It is noticed by many researchers, philosophers, thinkers that the trust is the key point of social communication. Trust can also be seen as a central element and cognitive basis of social cohesion (Budnik, 2018). Without the ability to trust other people and institutions and without understanding the need to meet the reasonable expectations of partners, effective social interaction, which is the basis of socio-cultural communication, becomes problematic. The specific function of trust as a “suggestive” gateway in human communication is considered in sociological and socio-psychological terms by a number of researchers, who noted the presence of a psychological opposition of trust / distrust. So, the trust can be attributed not only to the categories of sociological, political and psychological, but also to the social sphere, in particular, communicative, because trust is a condition of socio-cultural communication based on interaction. So, we can define, that a trust is a basic element of civil society, because the basic forms of civil society are voluntary forms of associations that exist outside the state. Such communities are based on trust as a mandatory element (Doktorova, 2014). So, it is quite important task for researchers to investigate complex relations and social impacts of trust as a key value of social cultural sphere.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article is to show, how nowadays is solving the very actual task for the thinkers, academicians and practitioners in overcoming challenges and threats of COVID-19 pandemic in the pedagogical, educational and social cultural spheres. According to this aim, there are the following objectives for the fundamental and practical researches in the social cultural space:

- to clarify and describe the existing and future challenges and threats of COVID-19 and its impact on to the security and sustainability of society;
- to find methodological and scientific foundations of the modern educational strategy and learning technologies for the social cultural managers in the conditions of pandemic COVID-19;
- to shape the new role of universities as engines of community development, cohesion and innovation processes for the economic and social cultural sustainable development;
- to aware of the changing of the social and cognitive niche of humans and its transferring to the virtual dimension.

One of the main tasks is to research in which way the values of trust and, accordingly, social cohesion are manifested in the social cultural space. How they can be measured, relied on and developed. It is also important to analyze some of the most important dimensions of social cultural space, in particular, educational space. The educational space, as a main part of the socio-cultural space, has to keep the dual focus for effective management of values. Implementation of values in the socio-cultural space could be realized correctly through university communities as a place of real interaction between the subjects of the socio-cultural space. In order to develop the social cohesion of the subjects of the educational space, certain measures should be taken, researches should be carried out, and pedagogical staff should be trained in educational institutions of different levels.

The methodological basis of the study is based on the systemic approach, methodology of sociology questionnaires and other research tools in the socio-cultural sphere. This article continues the research of the social cohesion phenomenon in the frame of Jean Monnet Module SCEGES. This project “Social Cohesion in Education and Governance: European Studies” is implementing in the National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. Academic coordinator of the project is Prof. Marja Nesterova, duration is 2017-2020. The social cohesion in education is one of the most perspective direction of social cohesion studies: EU Social Cohesion Policy, Social Cohesion Model, Social Cohesion Radar, etc. (Dragolov et al., 2013). This research also continues the study of the cognitive mechanisms of the complex social cohesion phenomenon started in the previous research of social cohesion in university community of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (Nesterova et al., 2019). Both these researches have practical focus on social cohesion in educational communities, which is quite complex and important problem of the sociocultural sphere. The methodological approach is technically based on the implementation of Social Cohesion Model at the level of educational communities. At the above researches this Model has been implemented for the social cohesion management of community of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. The obtained results allow concluding that the level of social cohesion in the university community of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University is quite sufficient. There are many reasons of it, which positively characterizes the attitude of employees and students to each other, reflects their readiness for mutual assistance and respect, acceptance of differences and tolerance, respect for social norms. However, there are some areas where the level of social cohesion of the whole university’s community can increase, and namely: achievement of indicators above average and high in all dimensions and domains (Nesterova et al., 2019).

Research methods. This research reflected and proved the confident role of education in the development of social cohesion of communities at the different dimensions of socio-cultural space. The authors of the research follow to the demand of further investigations. “Thus, the social cohesion in education could be considered from the focus of own connectedness of university community” (Nesterova et al., 2019). The Model of Social Cohesion by Bertelsmann Stiftung could be applied directly at the level of educational communities. Beside of the necessity to involve all stakeholders by interactive games’

Research information base. The complex analysis of the problem of trust and social cohesion is based on a well-developed scientific basis for studying key parameters for sustainable society development.

Our own empirical research was based at The Social Cohesion Model and author’s testing applied in the university community of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (Kyiv, Ukraine). The above research of social dimension of cognitive patterns of students and employees has been conducted in the university community to evaluate the real social cohesion level, which was not so confident in the National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. Therefore, the next investigations of the cognitive bases of social cohesion have to be provided (Nesterova et al., 2019).

The research information base is concerned on the analytics of sociological researches in the university communities.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The social cohesion and the trust are mutual determined

As we mentioned in the Model of Social Cohesion one of the parameter is “connectedness” – the basic of cohesive and trust relations. Both a social cohesion and trust are not only key values but social phenomenon. The trust is a cognitive, evolutionary mechanism of connectedness and cohesion in the various social groups. At the same time, one of the definitions of a complex societal phenomenon – social cohesion – includes “the level of trust and understanding of shared principles among groups in a society” (Roberts-Schweitzer, 2006). This research is focused on the educational dimension of social cultural space. Educational space is the “first link” of the war for every conscious person, for every active citizen. Education is a drive to assimilation of new values and through this education achieves the principal goal growing-up of a person with strong cultural background, with open mind. Also educational space is the key point of social tension and the sample of social cultural space. Education has the duty to decrease the social unrest (Spulber, 2018). For this purpose, the

concept of value-oriented (or value-based) education has been developed for the direct practical implementation of values in the educational space: both at the individual level (students, teachers) and at the community level (university community) and processes (teaching). Value-oriented learning just creates real channels through which values can be introduced, respectively, into the social cultural space. Values of the XXI society (as competencies too) should be transversal. Fragmentation and branching are becoming one of the most important and vulnerable features of the world community. That is why it is now necessary to find a common value platform (or transversal axis) for representatives of all segments of society. It is important to remember that the modern socio-cultural space is a denial and reappraisal of old values and even more – the search for new ways to preserve and transmit cultural experience. These forms may be associated with the decline of traditional and the simultaneous emergence of other (possibly new) socio-cultural structures (Stepanov, 2014). Both for effective differentiation and for building these new social cultural structures, it is necessary to be able to create and disseminate common senses. That is why the sense-forming competence (ability to discover and build senses) is so important: the ability to find the deepest or most important senses (meanings) in joint communication (Nesterova, 2019).

Common senses take us to another level of consideration of social systems. Thus, a system approach to the study of social cultural communications, which forms a social cultural space, leads us to consider social cultural activity in general. Social cultural activity could be determined as cultural activity of social actors in relation to the creation of cultural values; development of creative abilities of individuals and service of their creative activity; communications – dissemination, preservation and public use of all types of cultural values (Sokolov, 2003). Necessary for the sustainable development of society is such social cultural activity that stimulates the adaptability of citizens to the fast changing social processes. “The development of a socially responsible active person is impossible without the awareness and mastery of social cultural space as a collective intellect, conditions of self-organization and self-development, as it provides the population with spiritual freedom and forms national self-consciousness” (Stepanov, 2014). It again turns us back not only to values but to competencies. In this context very actual is development of the development of competence that could be determined as social competence: necessary in social cultural communication ability to communicate with other people, deep and directly, to identify and stimulate the right reactions and interactions with them. This includes not only emotional competence, the ability to analyze and take into account the emotions of others and adapt their words,

tone and gestures. But, in addition, it includes social competence – as key skills of working together and building relationships of trust, which is necessary for cooperation with groups of people in different contexts, establishing effective dialogue. It should be stressed again that development of these competencies is impossible without development of the common values platform, and the trust, at first.

3.2. Social cohesion as a value-based complex social phenomenon and its measurement

In turn, social cohesion as a social phenomenon is based on a set of individual and collective values that help integrate modern, complex and diverse societies. A fairly obvious conclusion is that values are the drivers of human behavior, and they must occupy a significant space of all social innovation. The very phenomenon of social cohesion is complex and important for the knowledge and development of modern socio-cultural space.

Therefore, it should be noted that the problem of measuring the level of social cohesion, the main factors and factors remains relevant, as well as quantitative and qualitative studies of social cohesion in the socio-cultural environment. Therefore, an important task is to conduct research and develop and adapt an appropriate methodology that would effectively measure and, accordingly, develop key structural elements and processes of social cohesion. Thus, there is a problem of finding an appropriate methodology for studying social cohesion.

One of the options for measuring social cohesion in society is the methodology developed by Bertelsmann Stiftung, which is based on the creation of an index of social cohesion and comparison of its level among different countries. The importance of methodological and practical application of this model is determined by the fact that such a complex socio-cultural phenomenon as social cohesion cannot be measured directly, unlike, for example, physical indicators (temperature, density, connectivity, etc.). This approach of the Bertelsmann Stiftung has been successfully applied for social cohesion's measurements. Originally the methodology of Bertelsmann Stiftung has been published at the report "The Social Cohesion Radar – An international Comparison of Social Cohesion" (2013). The report contains the evaluation of the social cohesion level in 34 advanced societies (27 member states of the European Union¹ and seven other western OECD countries: Australia, Canada, Israel, New Zealand, Norway, Switzerland, and the US) during four time periods from 1989 to 2012. This research has been created to measure social cohesion and its nine dimen-

sions (Dragolov et al., 2013). The Model of Social Cohesion by Bertelsmann Stiftung consists of three domains of social cohesion and their respective dimensions. The description of this model is in *Table 1*.

Table 1. The dimensions of social cohesion and their guiding principles

Domain	Dimension	Guideline
Social relations	Social networks	People have strong, resilient social networks
	Trust in people	People have a high level of trust in others
	Acceptance of diversity	People accept others with the different lifestyles and values and lifestyles
Connectedness	Identification	People feel strongly connected to their country and identity with it
	Trust in institutions	People have a high level of confidence in social and political institutions
	Perception of fairness	People believe that society's goods are fairly distributed and that they are being treated fairly
Focus on the common good	Solidarity and helpfulness	People feel responsibility for others and are willing to help them
	Respect for social rules	People abide by the fundamental rules of society
	Civic participation	People participate in society and political life and enter into public discussions

Source: Social Cohesion Model (Dragolov et al., 2013)

It should be noted that the original model of social cohesion, the Radar of Social Cohesion, can be applied to communities of different levels, without emphasizing territorial coexistence. For example, in the National Pedagogical Drahomanov University the researchers of social cohesion phenomenon conducted a study in which this model was applied at the level of the university community (Nesterova et al., 2019). It used the author's questionnaire and,

respectively, primary data. But it is important to notice that the original Bertelsmann Stiftung's approach is based only on secondary data analysis. The peculiarity of the model "Radar of social cohesion" is the hierarchical structure of these indicators, which describe the complex concept of social cohesion. This is the structure of generalized domains, each of which is described by three areas; each of these three areas is described by indicators that can be measured separately.

Considering the structure, dimensions and features of the socio-cultural space we can determine some managing parameters or its key factors. In this context the social cohesion as a complex social concept could be described, respectively, as a complex system of parameters in the form of a number of individual indicators, which are combined into a common index. "Social characteristics (in our case, social cohesion) that cannot be directly measured are often called constructs and are measured by factors or hidden characteristics (Nesterova et al., 2019). Another dimension of the social cohesion, geopolitical or territorial, can be defined as the degree of social unity in a territorially defined geopolitical community. Social cohesion is a characteristic of the team living in the structure, not its individual members. A cohesive society can be characterized by reliable social relations, positive emotional connection of its members. It could be at the different levels of social systems – community or state and with the strong emphasis on the common good (Bondarenko et al., 2017).

One of the key values of social cohesion in terms of "cohesion" (often referred to as the social cohesion level parameter) is trust as not only a key value but also a social phenomenon. The ability to trust should be seen as a cognitive evolutionary mechanism of connections and cohesion in different social groups. There are complex studies of the phenomenon of trust, which provide a distinction between two levels of articulation of trust: functional (algorithms and methods of implementation) and substantive (procedures of understanding and interpretation). The division of trust into contractual, communicative and competent manifestations was initiated by *D. Reina* and *M. Reina* (2007). For our research of the values of social cohesion and trust is very important to mark, that the phenomenon of trust is determined at the functional level in accordance with the purpose of this activity: subjectivity, community, organization / institution, management. At the same time, the substantive level of trust indicates different ways of conceptualizing it. However, these authors were convinced that the content of trust is not limited to these motivational components. There are other concepts of trust, its components and directions of manifestation and social functions. Trust is a complex

hierarchical social phenomenon that reflects a certain value attitude, which has the character of expecting the desired result and is based on confidence in the correctness and effectiveness of the object of trust, recognition of its activities that meet their own interests. There are three types of trust: to yourself, to other people, to the world. They also distinguish between interpersonal trust (as trust in people) and institutional trust (as trust in abstract systems) (Doktorova, 2014).

We can assume that trust performs an extremely important function in the socio-cultural space, in particular, in socio-cultural communications. Undoubtedly, trust can be considered the basis of social cohesion. One of the definitions of the social cohesion as complex social phenomenon includes the level of trust and understanding of the common principles between various groups of the society (Reina & Reina, 2007). The Social Cohesion Model by Bertelsmann Stiftung considers the trust as a main sphere of the social cohesion definition. This approach allows including the concept of trust to the complex and meaningful spheres of the social cohesion according to the Model. Also it confirms our considerations of trust and social cohesion as key parameters of the sociocultural space. It is confirmed by the evidence of two spheres – “Social Relations” and “Connectedness”. It has been shown in the *Table 1* that the one of the Bertelsmann Stiftung’s Model main domains – the domain “Social Relations” – includes “trust to people” and another one of the main Model’s domains – the domain “Connectedness” – includes the trust to institutions (Dragolov et al., 2013). In the behaviour patterns in the socio-cultural communication we can observe the importance of this parts of the trust.

This article is based on some previous investigations of the social cohesion phenomenon and its cognitive bases which are conducted in the frame of implementation of the Jean Monnet Module SCEGES in the National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. There were some researches of the level of social cohesion and the level of trust in the university communities. One of them was the research of the level of social cohesion in the university community of NPDU (Nesterova et al., 2019) and another research regarding on the level of trust in the university communities of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (NPDU) and National University of Life and Environmental Sciences (NULES) (Nesterova et al., 2020). This research has been held among the employees of the above universities (mostly lecturers) and students. The aim of the research is to identify the level of trust in the above communities and to mark the weak points in the domains of trust for further strengthening of it by appropriate trainings and other social and educational tools (Nesterova et al., 2020). According to this research we can confirm the

statement that one of the key factors of the social cultural space development is based on the appropriate values, trust, in particular. The social cohesion development sufficiently impacts on to the social cultural space development. The social cohesion in the community depends on the level of social interactions between members, their trust to each other, it is obvious. But also the social cohesion depends on the trust to institutions. Even before pandemic, the radical socio-economic transformations in Ukraine required the establishment of fundamentally new social relations. It is necessary to have a positive balance of public trust and distrust both at the personal level and at the level of social strata. “For example, it is quite obvious that such a social factor as distrust of power can be followed by a national crisis, and a change in the type of power, and the collapse of society as a manifestation of extreme distrust in the inaction of the authorities” (Glebova, 2015, p. 16). Unfortunately, we see how the above is now coming true – the first tests of crisis emergencies showed, first of all, distrust of the authorities and related manifestations of insufficient civic position (with the arising trend of antisocial behavior), which has a wide spectrum: from completely safe, frivolous pole to absolutely panic.

All above conducted researches have a practical meaning. Their application can be useful for the development of social and emotional intelligence among teachers and students, social cohesion and trust level development, In turn; they will be able to transmit new and productive interaction practices that are based on trust and cohesion (Nesterova et al., 2020). It could sufficiently improve the educational community development and the sociocultural space development accordingly.

4. Conclusions

As a result of the study, the following conclusions can be provided.

1. The results of the study, which are based on both theoretical assumptions and the results of the practical surveys and other studies in the field of social cohesion and trust could be effectively applied in the socio-cultural space for the civic society development.

2. According to these results we can state, that the trust is the factor that increases the social cohesion and, respectively, improves the socio-cultural space development. Thus, sustainable cohesion processes are impossible without a certain level of trust that exists in a given community.

3. This means that the values of trust and social cohesion are important prerequisites and factors of social patterns of responsible civic behavior that form the socio-cultural space of today.

4. Manifestations of trust in socio-cultural communications are ambiguous, the phenomenon itself is complex, requiring thorough interdisciplinary research, praxiological aspects of the study of trust as a socially important spiritual phenomenon and a relatively independent socio-psychological phenomenon are important. It seems to be confident that the indicators of trust can act as indicators of the communicative state of the individual, group and society as a whole.

5. Important factors in the development of socio-cultural space – trust and social cohesion, at the same time, act as certain indicators of social status in its communicative focus. Effective socio-cultural communications that shape the social cultural space are based on the values of trust and social cohesion.

6. Certain challenges of today require not only research, but also practical methods of implementation, development of its trust and social cohesion of different levels of communities.

7. Important tasks in this direction are assigned to the educational sphere, in particular, university communities, in which a stimulating socio-cultural environment is formed, which promotes the implementation of values, in particular, trust and social cohesion, which our society so desperately needs.

The scientific novelty of the research results is based on practical investigations, author's methodology of current situation. During the quarantine the educational space is getting different because of the on-line teaching & learning processes, social (physical) distancing between teachers and students, lack of non-virtual communication between students etc. In general, the scientific novelty of the research results is confirmed by systematic approach, understanding the essence of the social dimensions of cognitive patterns of behavior which in case of innovative transformation processes will have a sufficient impact on to the socio-cultural components of the modern society.

The practical significance of the obtained results could be obtained as a result of practical investigation of social cohesion tools as community development tools. During the described earlier projects the appropriate learning and researching challenges will be shaped. According to the inner logic of the project, we can formulate and offer scientific ideas, offers any possibilities and conclusions can be used for the decision of actual problems of communities and/or other organizations.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction need further study of the social cohesion model at national level. Therefore, at the near future the similar value surveys and investigation of intercultural dialogue will be launched between various universities (including EU). Also, the transformation of individual set of values should be caused by pandemic challenges of Covid-19. In continuation, an investigation of the level of trust in the various social-cultural

spheres (in particular, at the university community) could be considered as a quite important task for the future studies. The aim of the prospective researches is to test and analyze any possible changes in the educational communities because of pandemic impacts. This research will give us new important information about managing parameters of a social cultural space, in particular, values of trust and social cohesion as a key driver of social behavior in various situations of social challenges.

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